

Coastal Vulnerability Index Assessment along the Coastline of Casablanca using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques

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Supplementary Materials

Detailed descriptions of the point 0 considered for the showcase of the extraction of the coastal erosion metrics; the location of the 1630 points analysed on the coast of Casablanca; the significance (p-value) values of the linear relationship between annual shoreline positions and the annual observations; the standard error of the linear relationship between annual shoreline positions and the annual observations; and Charts depicting annual shoreline positions (cross-shore distances) for each point located on the beaches of Madame Choual, Ain Diab, Anfa, Ain Sebaa, Nahla, and Zenata beaches, Casablanca, Morocco are presented below:

Supplementary Materials A

Supplementary Materials S.1

The point 0 located on the beach of Zenata.

This point was considered to showcase the extraction of the coastal erosion metrics namely annual shoreline distances, shoreline change envelope (SCE), net shoreline movement (NSM), linear regression rate (LRR) and end point rate (EPR). At this point, annual shoreline distances represent the position of shoreline for each year from 2000 to 2023 as presented on Table S1. The year 2023 was considered as a reference to calculate the cross-shore distances. Positive distance values indicate that shorelines were located toward the ocean from 2023 while Negative distance values indicate that shorelines were located further inland. The SCE was computed by estimating the distance between the year in which the shoreline was the most landward (2010) and the year in which the shoreline was most seaward (2017). The NSM was calculated by calculating the distance between the shoreline position for the most recent year 2023 and the shoreline position for the old one (2000). For metrics LRR and EPR, their calculations were done by applying equations 1 and 3 as presented on Figure 5.

Table S1. detailed description for the point 0 used as example to calculate the LRR and EPR from cross-shore annual shoreline distance values (DIST_).

Field attribute	Value
DIST_2000	-14.24 (m)
DIST_2001	-38.3 (m)
DIST_2002	-1.59 (m)
DIST_2003	-25.13 (m)
DIST_2004	-15.3 (m)
DIST_2005	-6.19 (m)
DIST_2006	-10.13 (m)
DIST_2007	-9.24 (m)
DIST_2008	-14.81 (m)
DIST_2009	-19.85 (m)

DIST_2010	-39.21 (m)
DIST_2011	-26.69 (m)
DIST_2012	-20.09 (m)
DIST_2013	-2.05 (m)
DIST_2014	-0.47 (m)
DIST_2015	-2.05 (m)
DIST_2016	1.7 (m)
DIST_2017	3.36 (m)
DIST_2018	-0.27 (m)
DIST_2019	0.52 (m)
DIST_2020	-0.62 (m)
DIST_2021	0.89 (m)
DIST_2022	-3.08 (m)
DIST_2023	0 (m)
LRR	1.04 (m/yr)
EPR	0.62 (m/yr)
SCE	42.57 (m)
NSM	14.24 (m)

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Supplementary Materials S.2

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The location of the 1630 points analysed on the coast of Casablanca (Figure S1).

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Figure S1. 1630 points measured on the coast of Casablanca with 30 m of interval. They are labelled from 0 in the NE to 1629 in the SW.

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Supplementary Materials S.3

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The map (Figure S2) shows the significance (p-value) values of the linear relationship between annual shoreline distances and annual observations (time) estimated on the coast of Casablanca. Small values (e.g. p-value < 0.01) identified mainly of the sandy beaches indicate that the shoreline is undergoing consistent coastal changes from 2000 to 2023.

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Figure S2. significance (p-value) values of the linear relationship between annual shoreline distances and time estimated on the coast of Casablanca.

Supplementary Materials S.4

The map (Figure S3) shows the standard error of the linear relationship between annual shoreline distances and the annual observations (time) estimated for statistical analyses of rates of change conducted off the coast of Casablanca. These values can be used to generate confidence intervals around the rate of change given by the rate (time). As an example 95% confidence interval equals to standard error (time) multiple by 1.96.

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Figure S3. Standard error of the linear relationship between annual shoreline distances and the annual observations (time).

Supplementary Materials B

Charts depicting annual shoreline positions (cross-shore distances) for each point located on the beaches of Madame Choual, Ain Diab, Anfa, Ain Sebaa, Nahla, and Zenata beaches, Casablanca, Morocco. For each point, distances observed for each year from 2000 to 2023 are represented. On these graphs you can identify the year on which the shoreline was the most landward; the year on which the shoreline was the most seaward; the period when the coastline was relatively stable, retreating or growing. You can also estimate the approximate distance at which the shoreline shifted from 2000 and maximum change of the shoreline.

Supplementary Materials S.5

Figures S4, S5, S6, S8 illustrate the annual shoreline distances for each point considered on the beach of Madame Choual as presented in Figure A1. The charts have been drawn by considering every shoreline position from 2000 to 2023. On this beach, the shoreline was relatively stable from 2008 to 2014 at about 10 m toward the land compared to the 2023 location. For most of the points, the shoreline was the most landward in 2001.

Figure S4. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1266 to the point 1309 with an interval of 30 m

Figure S5. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1488 to the point 1502 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S6. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1503 to the point 1517 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S7. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1518 to the point 1521 with an interval of 30 m

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Supplementary Materials S.6

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Figures S8, S9, S10, S11, S12 illustrate the annual shoreline distances for each point considered on the beach of Ain Diab beach as presented in Figure A2. The charts have been drawn by considering every shoreline position from 2000 to 2023. On this beach, the shoreline was relatively dynamic inland with most landward shoreline of about 87 m in 2009 (on the point 1358).

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Figure S8. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1356 to the point 1370 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S9. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1371 to the point 1385 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S10. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1386 to the point 1400 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S11. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1401 to the point 1415 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S12. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1416 to the point 1426 with an interval of 30 m

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Supplementary Materials S.7

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Figures S13, S14, S15 illustrate the annual shoreline distances for each point considered on the beach of Anfa as presented in Figure A3. The charts have been drawn by considering every shoreline position from 2000 to 2023. On this beach, the shoreline was relatively stable from 2009 to 2012 at about 20 m toward the land compared to the 2023 location.

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Figure S13. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1266 to the point 1280 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S14. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1281 to the point 1295 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S15. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 1296 to the point 1309 with an interval of 30 m

Supplementary Materials S.8

Figures S16, S17, S18 illustrate the annual shoreline distances for each point considered on the beach of Ain Sebaa as presented in Figure A4. The charts have been drawn by considering every shoreline position from 2000 to 2023. On this beach, the shoreline was relatively stable from 2003 to 2010 toward the land with shoreline most landward in 2013 (point 252).

Figure S16. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 210 to the point 224 with an interval of 30 m

Figure S17. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 225 to the point 239 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S18. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 240 to the point 252 with an interval of 30 m

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Supplementary Materials S.9

Figures S19, S20, S21, S22, S23, S24, S25 illustrate the annual shoreline distances for each point considered on the beach of Nahla as presented in Figure A5. The charts have been drawn by considering every shoreline position from 2000 to 2023. On this beach, the shoreline was relatively stable from 2004 to 2009.

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Figure S19. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 118 to the point 132 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S20. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 133 to the point 147 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S21. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 148 to the point 162 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S22. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 163 to the point 177 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S23. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 178 to the point 192 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S24. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 193 to the point 207 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S25. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 208 to the point 212 with an interval of 30 m

Supplementary Materials S.10

Figures S26, S27, S28, S29, S30 illustrate the annual shoreline distances for each point considered on the beach of Zenata as presented in Figure A6. The charts have been drawn by considering every shoreline position from 2000 to 2023. On this beach, the shoreline was relatively dynamic toward the land. For most of the points, the shoreline was the most landward in 2014.

Figure S26. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 0 to the point 14 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S27. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 15 to the point 29 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S28. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 30 to the point 44 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S29. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 45 to the point 59 with an interval of 30 m

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Figure S30. Annual shoreline positions for each point labelled from point 60 to the point 75 with an interval of 30 m

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